

Scenario of Sports: Culture and Career in Urban and Rural India

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Abstract: The present study focuses on scenario of sports in urban and rural India. Sports plays an important role in development of a person and is equally important as academics and education. This article highlights various challenges, hurdles and achievements sportsman all over face and overcome to fulfil their dreams. Although a career in sports is not everyone's cup of tea, as it require immense efforts, hard work and sacrifices not only by the player but also by his family. Above that there remain some factors like physical strength, luck, patriotism, favourism etc. However this article is a small attempt to encircle various aspects leading in games & sports field.

Keywords: Sports, academics, challenges, physical strength, favourism.

Introduction: There goes a popular Indian proverb 'khelegekudoge to banogekharab, padhogelikhoge to banogenawab' (literally meaning education and studies is what matters and is important, games and sports has no future and will lead to nowhere)...till recent decades parents, relatives and teachers taunted and pressurised kids who showed interest in games and sports. But times have changed now. The article highlight on sports culture and this career in both urban and rural India.

Objective of the Study:

To study the sport culture in urban and rural areas of India.

To study various problems faced by the sportsmen.

Methodology of the Study:

Secondary data was used for the research study. The source for secondary data has been through books, articles, internet.

Career in Sports:

More importantly post globalisation and induction of open economy in the last decade of last century when satellite transmission and network of channels flooded worldwide, sports economy, fan following and career in sports have boomed like any other flourishing industry or profession. The primary reason why middle-and-lower class parents in sub-continent feared sports career was the fact that parents always prefer secured life than an adventurous life. Also India lacked sports culture and appropriate sporting ecosystem hence sports in those days wasn't in general a luxury as a career option economically. It's good that nowadays, parents are thinking beyond traditional job options and even educational institutions are encouraging students to take up sports as career. Though the competition, complexity, expenses and vulnerability hasn't diminished, but the scope, facilities and platforms to select a sport to achieve your dreams have certainly increased.

Games and Sports not only gives name, fame and wealth but it helps individual development

as a human being and can also play an eminent role in communal development, which fosters economic growth. Hence the increased exposure and visibility, revenue, and job possibilities that sports provide contribute to stimulating State or National development. The popularity of sportsperson has huge magnitude on which sponsor's and advertisement industry rely upon.

Insufficient Sport Environment:

All said and done the most important point arises selection of sport? Which sport a kid would like to or should select or become fond of to play it as a hobby and convert that hobby into a career. Unfortunately India's national sport 'Hockey' is completely overlooked to the point that people in and out of India believe 'Cricket' is our national sport. Cricket is played by few and worshipped and breathed by millions. Hence by default lot of kids (and parents too) opt for Cricket if it has to be taken as career. The infra structure and environment for Cricket is far more positive with respect to academies, facilities, stadiums, tournaments and other services, as compared to other sports. BCCI (Cricket Control Board in India) has done a great job in promoting and popularizing cricket throughout the nation.

Introduction of IPL and T20s have further contributed to its popularity and economical success. The fanaticism which India shows during IPL season or world cup's is unbelievable, however we shouldn't forget that there are also other sports and they merit the same respect, appreciation and support. Equal consideration must be granted and encouraged to other sports too. Apart from BCCI all other sporting bodies like Sports Authority in India (SAI), India Olympic Committee (IOC), Mission Olympic cell (MOC), other working regulatory bodies such as AIFF, HI, IHF, etc. are all disorganized and unmethodical and are mostly occupied grappling with internal issues. Also their

financial systems are often low and have miserably struggled and are not even near to BCCI. They should take a leaf out of BCCI handbook, in spotting the talent at younger age almost in inter-School competitions, focussing on modernising sports infrastructure at the grassroots, providing scientific training to young athletes, helping them with modern technology, top-quality facilities, world class coaches and climatic conditions. Such a conducive environment will help young talent to train without any distractions that can affect their training schedule. Though National Centres of Excellence (NCoE), 'Khelo India' are some promising steps taken in that direction but it is not sufficient to imbibe a complete sporting environment.

Hurdles in Sports:

The hurdle in other sports development in India probably might be Cricket. Cricket has rose to such a high peak that it is feared that if cricket mania persists in India, we will never be able to do well in other sports. India is the largest-most populated nation behind China. Raw Talent, skilful aspirants, enthusiasm and sportsman spirit are at abundant. However it is highly disappointing that India apart from achievement in cricket is unable to convert performances into a success in other sports or at the Olympic, Common Wealth Games etc.

Indian Hockey team in the golden era when Dhyanchand and Co played on grass grounds rather than on AstroTurf's played today, had ruled the sport. Apart from that so far India have earned 9 gold medals, 6 silver medals and 11 bronze medals since the 1900 Paris Olympic games; with a pathetic tally of about 26 medals at Olympics. By contrast, China, has won 201 gold medals, 144 silver medals and 128 bronze medals, touching a total of around 473 medals. This pronounced difference has one rather simple explanation, aside from cricket, authorities, athletes and parents are not stressing or believing in any other sports apart from Cricket. We can't play some game of guilt here because it's our culture that's liable for this circumstance.

Sports: Gap between Urban and Rural

Another extremely important issue faced in India is emergence of talent from Urban and Rural parts. In recent past lot of Indian sporting talent have emerged from non- metropolitan cities or small towns of rural India where they have limited access to training, resources and guidance. Even in Cricket for decades teams of Bombay (Mumbai), Delhi, Bangalore (Bengaluru), Madras (Chennai) had upper hand on premier National championships and representation in Indian Team. However in last 1-2 decades players from small towns have made it big and been pillars of the team. Likes of Mahendra Singh Dhoni (Ranchi), Suresh Raina (Meerut), Zahir Khan (Shrirampur), Mohammad Shami (Amroha),

Sanju Samson (Pulluvila) Umran Malik (Srinagar), Harmanpreet Kaur (Moga), Jhulan Goswami (Chakdaha), Mithali Raj (Jodhpur) have taken sports following to next level. Also some of the star players from other sports like P.T.Usha (Pilavullakandi Thekkeparambil), Anju Bobby George (Cheeranchira), Bhaichung Bhutia (Tinkitam), Deepika Kumari (Ram Chatti, near Ranchi), Karnam Malleswari (Srikulam), Mary Kom (Kangathe, Manipur), Mirabai Chanu (Imphal) have defeated all odds to achieve success and become poster stars for the schools & Colleges. They have also given a huge momentum for other kids to take sports as a profession. In the small towns, actual ground reality pertaining to sports preference is strictly regarded as an "Extracurricular activities" and not a part of curriculum, career prospect not at all.

Environment and society in rural India till recently was not conducive for sports, As the parents have their own miseries to survive & earn bread & butter. Adding the expenses of training fees, travelling and necessary sporting equipments (example a complete set of proper Cricket Kit can be in the range of INR 8000 - 10,000 and above !!!), parents certainly buckle under such cost and assurance of success when it comes to big time career. However with the emergence of above names, society, relatives, neighbours and schools have developed Self belief. This is one important factor in new generation parent that they inculcate belief and support their children. Parents from rural India are now more open to take risks not only in sports but also in various Television reality shows for dancing, singing, and other talent exploring creative activities.

A Pan-India survey was conducted by Community platform Local Circles to find and track the impact of the success of Tokyo Olympics on Indian society. A high percentage (71%) of Indian families said that they would support their children should they choose to pursue any other sports as careers other than cricket. Traditionally, most middle-class parents have been reluctant to support their children to take up sports outside cricket as a career with the belief that they do not provide regular earnings and financial stability in the long term. However, Tokyo Olympics instilled new and fresh energy into the prospects of non-cricket sports in India. The community platform used responses from 18,000 participants belonging to 309 districts across the country. Around 40% of respondents were from tier 1 districts, while almost 60% from Tier 2, 3, 4 and rural districts. Which clearly underlines that the rural India is seriously focussing on sports as a career alternative, which is also evident from the fact that more of the sporting icons are arising from rural parts of India than the metropolitan cities.

These naturally gifted and talented kids rise above all the odds and stamp a mark on all sports. Further to strengthen above fact, Pandemic (Covid-19) has impacted hugely for the diminishing ground or sports activity in cities as compared to rural India. "Work/School from home" have had lack of physical activity among school students which is a big concern for parents, teachers and educationists and fear a negative impact over the long-term. Children have adapted to learn and make use of electronic devices. But apart from just studies they are developing an addiction. With less physical activities on ground they may lead to obesity, mental health issues, getting engaged in personal virtual world, avoiding outer circles, competition, sportsman spirit and also denial of sharing etc. These are topics of worry amongst the urban young generation. To worsen the situation, generally the urban schools prioritise more academics, projects, work sheet over sports activity, with students not getting time to play during school period or otherwise, in the longer run may result in complete loss of their interest towards games & sports. Many Physical educators and experts believe that with lack of games and competitions, development of crucial social skills and team spirit in children are also affected. Today urban children are more proficient on handling of electronic gadgets like Smartphones, iPhone, laptops but lack physical strength and muscle building in the young age. To add to it various global companies keep on introducing newer Apps for online Games for their vested interested and the urban kids fall prey to it.

Policy Measures:

With continual of such scenario, India will certainly miss out on young sporting talents from urban cities and it may take some time for children to be motivated to take up sports again. Schools & colleges should induce interest & importance of games to students by holding inter school competitions, identify and groom talented athletes in various sports. This process is greatly hampered in past couple of years owing to urban education pattern, study burden, busy schedules, coaching classes, practical's, seminars etc and more profoundly due to advent of COVID pandemic, when whole sporting activity were put on hold. However the Governing bodies, educationists, institutionist need to regain the lost ground. Sports authorities should Identify areas of improvement across sports so that India find hidden talent and ensure this talent prepares for the best competitions and against the best sports persons globally and make our nation proud and keep our Tricolour flying high.

Conclusion:

Sports is not just entertainment or a part time activity. It is a serious business and testing

profession and in a way part of our existence and culture. Sports appreciates talent irrespective of caste, religion, male, female, rural or urban and even economical backgrounds. It is of utmost importance that a nation should achieve glory in the sporting domain because all its citizens find pleasure in the triumphs achieved by its sportsman. Many grieving social issues like unemployment, price hikes, or communal distrust have halted during Cricket series or progress of India Hockey Team during Tokyo Olympics atleast for some time. This is strength of sports. Sports make people optimistic and help build sportsman spirit and communal harmony. No matter urban or rural, success in sports events may it be cricket World Cup or Olympics, Asiad, Common wealth games, Sports brings a nation to a common place. A nation which is such diverse with respect to culture, language, food habits, festivals, and even many socio-economic uncertainties, feel proud and equal with the success in Games and Sports achievement. To the generation next sports career may genuinely be a serious profession or way of life same as some other mainstream options like Engineering, Medical, Architecture, Law, defence services etc. Children from rural parts in recent times have believed sporting career as a new means to liberate their talent, and way to change their fortunes. The poster icons who have rose from rural parts or tier 2, 3 towns in numerous sporting events have unexpectedly changed the scenario of Indian sports culture. Its time now that children from urban parts and metropolitan cities balance their workload and life style and take up sports as a career. Infact the facilities, options and financial back-up for them are wide and easy. The only thing required is inner belief, positive frame of mind and immense hard work.

Let's hope for a better future for sporting India in which talent rises from urban and rural India together and make our nation a force to reckon in all sports and all major sporting events and our sporting stars earn lots of trophies and medals to make India proud.

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